

RCS MODEL OF EM BACKSCATTERING FROM OBJECTS WITH NONLINEAR MOTION DYNAMICS

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Introduction

The purpose of this work is to simulate electromagnetic (EM) backscattering from objects with nonlinear motion dynamics, such as a heavy top with precession motion, a spinning gyrosopic, or a swinging pendulum, and to analyze modulations induced by the nonlinear motion dynamics.

Radar cross section (RCS) of an object is a function of aspect angle and frequency. When the object is rotating or has a rotating structure on it, the EM backscattering is subject to modulations simultaneously in amplitude and phase that result in asymmetric Doppler spectra about the carrier frequency. The characteristics of the spectra are determined by the geometry, dimension, and the rotation rate of the rotating part.

Nonlinear Motion Dynamics

To derive EM backscattering from a rigid body undergoing nonlinear motion dynamics, we must first solve a set of Euler's motion differential equations [1, 2]. With the ordinary differential equations (ODE) and given initial Euler angles (precession, nutation and spin) $\psi, \theta,$ and φ in the fixed body coordinates, initial Euler angles' velocity $\omega_1, \omega_2,$ and ω_3 with respect to the body coordinates, and physical characteristics of the object and its environment: principle moments of inertia $I_1, I_2,$ and I_3 respect to the fixed body coordinates, mass $m,$ gravitational force $g,$ and distance from center of mass to point of rotation $L,$ the data defining the nonlinear motion can be generated by

$$\begin{aligned}(I_1 + mL^2)\dot{\omega}_1 &= (I_2 - I_3 + mL^2)\omega_2\omega_3 + mgL \cos\varphi \sin\theta \\(I_2 + mL^2)\dot{\omega}_2 &= (I_3 - I_1 - mL^2)\omega_1\omega_3 - mgL \sin\varphi \sin\theta \\I_3\dot{\omega}_3 &= (I_1 - I_2)\omega_1\omega_2\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

For example, a spinning cone with initial external forces will precess about an axis with a certain angular velocity. Under gravity a spinning heavy top with a fixed point will have precession motion about an axis as shown in Fig.1, where $m = 25$ kg, $L = 0.563$ m, $I_1 = I_2 = 0.117$ kg m² and $I_3 = 8.5$ kg m², and the dynamic Euler angles, angular velocities, and the trajectory of the center of mass as shown in the figure.

RCS Model of EM Backscattering

Consider the motion of the object as a sequence of snapshots taken at each time instant to estimate the variation of the EM backscattering field as if the object were static. To simulate the nonlinear motion, the source is manually positioned around a stationary object at individual time intervals. This can allow for the simulation of arbitrary motion of the target by creating of a false sense of target movement when viewed from the stationary frame of the EM source. It is very helpful then to first transform the data of nonlinear motion into a sequence of camera viewing angles, which can be used to move a simulated camera around a stationary 3D model representing the radar target.

We use this quasi-static EM modeling and incorporate solution of a set of rigid body motion equations into the EM simulation. The Integral Radar Target Signature (IRTS) computational electromagnetics code, developed at NRL [3], is primarily used for RCS prediction utilizing a multitude of different backscattering algorithms, including geometrical optics, physical optics, physical theory of diffraction, and method of moments solutions. Through post-processing, it can also yield magnitude and phase information at individual scatter centers or range cells and other relevant data. Fig. 2 shows EM backscattered radar I&Q raw data and range profiles of a heavy top with precession.

Time-Varying Micro-Doppler Signatures

When a signal is reflected from a rotating target, the frequency spectrum of the signal may indicate the presence of Doppler modulation. The Doppler modulation can be observed by deviations of the frequency spectrum from the returned carrier frequency. Due to lack of localized time information, the Fourier transform cannot provide more complicated time-varying frequency modulation information. A joint time-frequency analysis that provides localized time-dependent frequency information is needed for extracting time-varying motion dynamic features. To analyze the time-varying frequency characteristics of the Doppler modulation and visualize the localized joint time and frequency information, the signal must be analyzed by using a high-resolution time-frequency transform, which characterizes the temporal and spectral behavior of the analyzed signal [4]. Fig.3 shows time-varying micro-Doppler signature of the modulations induced by nonlinear motion dynamics of the heavy top.

References:

- [1] E.W. Weisstein. Euler Angles. *Mathworld-A Wolfram Web Resource*, 1999.
- [2] M.A. Trindade and R. Sampaio. On the numerical integration of rigid body nonlinear dynamics in presence of parameters singularities. *J. Braz. Soc. Mech. Sci.*, 23(1):49-62, 2001.
- [3] W. P. Pala, H. J. Bilow, W. B. Gordon, D. A. Zolnick, S. A. Zuro, and V. W.

Strasser, "Integral Radar Target Signature Model," NRL Memorandum Report 6187, Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, DC, Apr. 1988.
 [4] V.C. Chen and H. Ling. *Time-Frequency Transforms for Radar Imaging and Signal Analysis*. Norwood, MA: Artech House, 2002.

Fig.1 A spinning heavy top with precession motion.

Fig.2 EM backscattered radar I&Q raw data and range profiles of a heavy top with precession motion.

Fig.3 Time-varying micro-Doppler signature of the heavy top.